

A Comprehensive Review on: Lozenges

Sumit Surendra Kolte, Dr. Dharmendra Jain

Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Dr. Harisingh Gour Vishwavidyalaya
(Central University, A+ grade by UGC NAAC) Sagar, Madhya Pradesh, 470003.

Abstract: - Lozenges have long been utilized as a popular and effective delivery method for pharmaceuticals due to their convenience, palatability, and localized action. This comprehensive review examines the diverse applications of lozenges in pharmaceuticals, encompassing their roles in soothing sore throats, delivering medications for respiratory conditions, managing oral health, and addressing nutritional deficiencies. Lozenges are one of the widely used dosage forms. The benefits of the medicated lozenges is that they increase the retention time of the dosage form in the oral cavity which increases bioavailability, reduces gastric irritation and bypasses first-pass metabolism. This review evaluates the formulation considerations, such as flavouring agents, sweeteners, and active ingredients, that influence the efficacy and patient acceptance of lozenges. Furthermore, it explores emerging trends in lozenge design, including the integration of novel drug delivery systems and the incorporation of functional ingredients for enhanced therapeutic outcomes. By synthesizing current research findings and clinical evidence, this review aims to provide insights into the evolving landscape of lozenge-based therapies and their potential contributions to optimizing patient care and improving health outcomes.

Keywords: - Lozenges, Antitussives, Molding, Patient compliance, Congealing

1. Introduction

Lozenges are flavoured medical dosage forms with a sweetened base that are meant to be sucked and placed inside the mouth or pharynx. They typically contain one or more medications. Lozenges are used to treat oropharyngeal symptoms, which are frequently caused due to on by local infections. If the medication is adequately absorbed through the buccal linings or when taken in, it may also have a systemic effect [Pundir and Verma, 2014]. The word “Lozenge” is derived from the French word “Losenge” which means a diamond-shaped geometry having four equal sides. Lozenges and pastilles have been developed since the 20th century in pharmacy and are still under commercial production [Choursiya and Andheriya,2018]. They are frequently used to administer medications with topical anaesthetic and antibacterial effects and are usually used for throat pain and irritation [Kolap *et al.*,2021]. Lozenges come in numerous shapes, including flat, round, octagonal, and biconvex. Bacilli are often short rods or cylinders. Pastille is a soft lozenge made from gelatin or glycerogelatin, or a combination of acacia, sucrose, and water. Confections, now obsolete, are sugary soft masses with therapeutic properties [D. Peters,1989]. Solid absorbable lozenges typically have an absorption time of about 30 minutes; however, this can vary depending on the patient's absorption state. Suctioning and producing saliva can dilute drugs and lead to unintentional swallowing. The amount of medication administered with each lozenge application may vary significantly. Absorption and saliva production may dilute the medication and lead to unintentional swallowing [Ozakar *et al.*,2021]. Prescription and over-the-counter pain drugs might be challenging to prescribe for people who are resistant to typical oral treatments. Children and adults may struggle to swallow tablets or capsules. Patients may avoid taking liquid medications due to bad taste, texture, or difficulty swallowing [Khudhair and Ali,2020]. This can lead to significant fluctuation in the amount of medication supplied with each lozenge administration. Sucking and saliva production can dilute drugs and raise the risk of unintentional swallowing. Depending on the kind of lozenges, they are made by moulding or compression. Lozenges contain a variety of components, including candy base, binders, lubricants, flavoring, coloring, whipping agents, and humectants, among others. Some lozenges can be purchased over the counter without a prescription, while others require a prescription from a certified medical practitioner [Chandrawanshi *et al.*,2019].

2. Benefits of medicated lozenges

The following are the advantages of medicated lozenges:

- a) Can be given to those patients who have difficulty in swallowing.
- b) Easy to administer to geriatric and pediatric populations.
- c) Has pleasant taste [**Gopale *et al.*,2022**]
- d) It extends the time of the drug in the oral cavity to elicit a local effect [**Maheshwari *et al.*,2013**]
- e) Give systemic effect.
- f) Easy to prepare, with a minimum amount of equipment and time [**Choursiya and Andheriya,2018**].
- g) Do not require water intake for administration because most of its part absorbed through oral mucosa, preventing the degradation of the drug at gastric pH.
- h) Technique is non-invasive, as is the case with parenterals.
- i) Reduce xerostamia.
- j) It has the ability to bypass the first past metabolism.
- k) It has improved patient compliance [**Gopale *et al.*,2022**].

3. Challenges of medicated lozenges

The following some of the Challenges of medicated lozenges:

- a) High-calorie content
- b) A hard candy lozenge is the high temperature required for their preparation.
- c) The lozenge dosage form is that it mistakenly could be used as candy by children.
- d) Hard lozenges become grainy [**Shinde *et al.*,2014**].

4. Medicaments

Drug candidates which can be incorporated in lozenges, belong to one of the following categories [**Shinde *et al.*,2014**].

- a) Antiseptics
- b) Local anaesthetics
- c) Antibiotics
- d) Antihistaminic
- e) Antitussives
- f) Analgesics
- g) Decongestants

5. Types of Lozenges

There are some many types of candies are available in the market, the major types has been compiled up below:

a) **Compressed Tablet Lozenges**

If the active ingredient is heat labile, it may be made into lozenge preparation by compression. The granulation is prepared in a manner similar to that used for any compressed tablet. The lozenge tablets differ from conventional tablets in terms of organolepticity, non-disintegrating characteristics and slower dissolution. The lozenge is made using heavy compression equipment to give a tablet that is harder than usual, as it is desirable for the troche to dissolve slowly in mouth. [Bhowmik *et al.*,2009]

5.1. Method of Preparation of compressed tablet lozenges

- a) **Direct compression-** In this method, ingredients can be thoroughly mixed and directly compressed.
- b) **Wet granulation-** In this method sugar is pulverized by mechanical comminution to a fine powder (40-80 mesh). Medicament is added and the mass is blended mass. The blended is subjected to granulation with sugar or corn syrup and screened through the 2-8mesh screen. This is followed by drying and milling to 10-30mesh size. Flavour and lubricant are then added prior to the compression [Namdev *et al.*,2022].

Compressed tablet lozenges are prepared by developing three different methods under the wet granulation technique which include:

- i. **Ordered mixing:** Where a drug in a finely divided state is made to adhere to the coarser diluent particles by the application of frictional forces.
- ii. **Drug adsorption:** Involves the deposition of drug present in the solution on a solid.
- iii. **Drug excipient hybrid mixing by spray drying:** where liquid feed is rapidly transformed into a fine powder [Sharma *et al.*,2022].

5.1.1. Preparation of compressed tablet lozenges by the method of ordered mixing

The ordered mixture prepared by adding the sieved (80#) Drug in small parts to the weighed amount of Iso-malt and mixed thoroughly for 30 mins. Weighed amounts of other excipients added to the prepared ordered mixture taken in a mortar and granulated by wet granulation method using a 15% w/v binding agent. The dried granules retained on sieve#44 when passed through sieve#22 together with 15% fines mixed with weighed amounts of lubricant, glidant and spray-dried flavour compressed in a single punch machine with maximum force to obtain a compact flat-faced tablet lozenges [Sharma *et al.*,2022].

5.1.2. Preparation of compressed tablet lozenges of 10% drug adsorbate

Drug adsorbate (10%) prepared by adding 1 g of the drug in boiling water taken in a petri dish with constant stirring on a thermostatically controlled water bath. 10 g of activated magnesium trisilicate (obtained by vacuum drying at 100 °C and 720 mmHg for 24 hours) added to the above drug mixture and mixed thoroughly to obtain a homogenous dispersion. Finally, the mixture was oven-dried at 70 °C until the moisture content was less than 1.5%. The sieved free-flowing powder taken along with other excipients in a mortar and then compressed to lozenges by wet granulation method as explained above [Vyas *et al.*,2022].

5.1.3. Preparation of compressed tablet lozenges by using spray dried hybrid mixture of base and drug

Spray-dried hybrid mixture is prepared by separately dissolving a weighed quantity of base such as mannitol in distilled water, to which 10% w/w of the drug added with stirring. This homogenous solution is then fed into a mini spray drier using a pressure atomizer through a Rotating wheel with an atomizing air pressure of 5 kg/sq. inch. The inlet temperature (140/160 °C), feed pump speed (2/4 ml/min), aspirator level (20/40) and concentrations of mannitol (10%/20%) used carefully. Weighed quantity of this hybrid mixture was taken along with other excipients in a mortar, and then compressed to lozenges by wet granulation method as explained above [Kini and Rathnanand,2011].

b) Soft Lozenges

Soft lozenges are either meant for chewing or for slow dissolution in the mouth. They can be made from PEG 1000 or 1450, chocolate or sugar-acacia base while some soft lozenge formulations can also contain acacia and silica gel. Acacia is used to provide texture and smoothness to the lozenge and silica gel is used as a suspending agent to avoid settling of materials to the bottom of the mold cavity during the cooling. The formulation requires a heating process at about 50 °Celsius hence is only suitable to heat-resistant ingredients [Pothu and Yamsani,2014].

5.1.4. Preparation of Soft Lozenges

Soft lozenges are prepared by melting and mold technique as described previously. PEG melted on a water bath and mixed with the other ingredients to form a homogeneous mixture. Subsequently, the mixture was poured into the stainless-steel mold which size of each mold of tablet 12 mm in diameter and 6.8 mm in height.

c) Hard Candy Lozenges

Hard candy lozenges are mixtures of sugar and other carbohydrates in an amorphous (nanocrystalline) or glassy state. They can also be regarded as solid syrups of sugars. The

moisture content and weight of hard candy lozenge should be between, 0.5 to 1.5% and 1.5-4.5 g respectively. These should undergo a slow and uniform dissolution or erosion over 5-10 min and should not disintegrate. The temperature requirements for their preparation is usually high hence heat labile materials cannot be incorporated in them [Pothu and Yamsani, 2014].

5.1.5. Preparation of hard candy lozenges

The various steps involved in the preparation of tablet lozenges are the Preparation of syrup and maintenance of temp. at 150 °C till it becomes thick. The syrup is then placed in a vacuum chamber for about 30 minutes to remove the traces of water molecules and to give plasticity to the base prepared. The drug, mucoadhesive polymers, citric acid, colour and flavouring agents added manually and mixed thoroughly. Then this solidified mass placed between the rollers of the batch former to form a rope size and shape. Hot air was blown over the product (Lozenges) in the rotating drying chamber (velocity of 1500-3000 ft/min as the lozenges passed from the cooling belts) [Shivappa *et al.*, 2011].

5.1.6 Hard Candy Lozenges Raw Materials:

The types of raw materials used in medicated lozenges may vary according to a number of factors. Most medicated lozenges contain sugar, corn syrup, acidulant, colorant, flavour, and the medicament.

- a) **Sucrose:** Sucrose, a disaccharide of glucose and fructose, is obtained from sugarcane or beet. The choice of beet or cane sugar is based on availability and geographical considerations. Sucrose and sucrose products are used in medicated lozenges because of their value as neutral sweeteners, their ready solubility, and their function as a “drier” to reduce the weight of the confection through crystallization [Awad *et al.*, 2022].
- b) **Invert sugar:** Invert sugar, derived from sucrose, possesses the very desirable physical property of controlling the crystallization of concentrated sugar solutions and maintaining freshness of the finished product through its humectant properties [Gopale *et al.*, 2022].
- c) **Corn syrup:** Corn syrup is used in almost every type of confection to control sucrose and dextrose crystallization, which may lead to crumbling. Corn syrup in appropriate proportion with sucrose and dextrose allows the formation of an amorphous glass and produces a candy with the desirable appearance. The following physical properties of corn syrup are extremely important in the preparation of medicated candies: density, dextrose equivalent (DE), hygroscopicity, sugar crystallization, viscosity, freezing point depression, and osmotic pressure [Garg *et al.*, 2020].

- d) **Isomalt:** Isomalt is an almost equimolar mixture of 6- glucopyranosyl-sorbitol (6- GPS) and 1- glucopyranosyl-mannitol (1-GPM), and the weight percentage can vary between 43 to 57% of 6-GPS to 57% to 43% of 1-GPM. Isomalt has properties like a binding agent, i.e. to a certain extent it is capable of establishing binding between the individual particles in the composition and further in the binding during the kneading step in the process of preparing a lozenge. Isomalt is beyond being a binding agent also a suitable softener. The lozenges prepared with a binding agent comprising isomalt are softer than lozenges that do not contain any isomalt [**Choursiya and Indurkhya,2020**].
- e) **Colorants:** Colorants are incorporated into medicated lozenges for appearance, product identification, and masking of physical degradation [**Mishra *et al.*,2017**].
- f) **Dyes and other organic colourants:** Dyes and other organic colourants may degrade by heat or light via oxidation, hydrolysis, photo-oxidation, etc., and their compatibility with drug, excipients, and process conditions should be studied before selection. [**Wahyuni *et al.*,2023**].
- g) **Acidulants:** Acidulants are generally added to medicated lozenges to fortify and strengthen their flavor profile. Organic acids such as citric, malic, fumaric, and tartaric acids are most commonly used. Citric acid alone or in combination with tartaric acid is the most common. Another use of acids in medicated lozenges is to alter the pH to maintain the integrity of the drug. Regular conversion corn syrup has a pH of 5.0–6.0. Addition of a weak organic acid to improve flavor lowers it to 2.5–3.0, a pH at which some medicaments exhibit maximum stability. If necessary, some drugs can be stabilized by adjusting the pH to 7.0–8.0 with a suitable weak base such as calcium carbonate. Some research has shown that excessive use of acidic lozenges could have the potential to enhance existing dental erosion, and that low pH (2.6–3.7) leads to dissolution of calcium and phosphorous from hydroxyapatite. Others have shown that excessive use of citric and tartaric acids may affect bioavailability of zinc in zinc lozenges. Another report indicated that the activity of cetyl pyridinium chloride in candybase lozenges is influenced by pH, with >5.5 being most desirable. Acceptable taste is necessary to ensure patient acceptability, and this can be the determining factor between commercial success and failure of an OTC product [**Zainol *et al.*,2020**].
- h) **Flavors:** Flavors used in medicated lozenges must be compatible with the drug and excipients and capable of withstanding the rigors of the manufacturing conditions. Flavors consist of numerous chemicals that may interact with excipients or medicaments and that degrade by heat and light. Aldehydes, ketones, and esters may

react with drugs. A classic example of flavor–drug interaction is that of a primary amine drug (benzocaine, phenylpropanolamine) with aldehyde containing flavor components like cherry, banana, etc., resulting in the formation of a Schiff base, drug decomposition, and loss of efficacy. Adjustment of lozenge base pH to accentuate certain flavors (e.g., citrus) may also result in incompatibility with some medicaments (e.g., benzocaine) [Maskare *et al.*,2023].

- i) **Salvage:** The last major ingredient in lozenges is salvage obtained from lozenge batches rejected because of imperfect shape or size, presence of air bubbles, or unacceptable drug concentration. Salvage, if properly heated, can be reused in finished products without altering color, texture, lozenge base composition, or drug concentration. Before any salvage can be used as part of a medicated lozenge base, it should be adjusted to a pH of 4.5–7.5 to prevent excessive and uncontrolled formation of reducing sugars, and the stability of the drug at cooking cycles should be determined [Khaladkar *et al.*,2019].

d) Center Filled Hard Candy Lozenges

These are the hard candy lozenges with soft or liquid centers into their main body.

Table 1. Type of centre-filled lozenges [Pundir and Verma ,2014]

Sr.No.	Type of centre-filled lozenges	Composition	Fill weight (%)
1	Liquid fill	Fruit juice, sugar syrup, hydro alcoholic solutions or Sorbitol solution.	10-20
2	Fruit center	Jams and jellies whose viscosity has been modified with corn syrup or liquid sucrose	20-25
3	Paste center	Granules and crystals formulated as a paste	40
4	Fat center	Medicament or flavor being suspended or dissolved in hydrogenated vegetable oil	25-32

6. A WORLD OF SUGAR-FREE CANDY/LOZENGES

The sugar-free chewing gum market which incidentally first started as sugar-based and then switched completely to sugar-free – provides other confectionery segments with an interesting perspective on sugar-free market share development. In addition to chewing gum, sugar-free medicated confectionery – with its inherent health benefits – is also well positioned at 58% market share. At the same time, sugar-free mints, at 35%, demonstrate that the sugar-free trend is gaining momentum [Dineshmohan *et al.*,2010].

Over the years, interest in sugar-free confectionery has grown in parallel with tooth friendly concerns. In European countries, the prevalence of tooth decay has been decreasing and is now stable. For example, in the UK, it is 0.7. On the other hand, in Croatia it is 4.8. Any improvements tend to be the result of WHO- and government-supported hygiene campaigns promoting good nutrition, fluoride supplementation, teeth cleaning – three times a day is recommended – and regular visits to the dentist. Nevertheless, it is important to avoid snacking between meals on food containing fermentable sugars. Snacking is a common practice and sugar-free confectionery can help reduce its impact while keeping the habits enjoyable. [Dineshmohan *et al.*,2010]

Lozenges are formulated in such a way that they are stable, provide a good medium for administration of drugs. The ingredients which are used for formulation of Lozenges are as shown in table-2.

Table 2. Ingredients used for formulation of Lozenges [Pundir and Verma ,2014]

Ingredients	Examples
Candy base	
a) Sugar	Dextrose, sucrose, maltose, lactose.
b) Sugar-free vehicles	Mannitol, sorbitol, polyethylene glycol (PEG) 600 and 800.
c) Fillers	Dicalcium phosphate, calcium sulfate, calcium carbonate, lactose, microcrystalline cellulose.
Lubricants	Magnesium stearate, calcium stearate, stearic acid and PEG, vegetable oils and fats.
Binders	Acacia, corn syrup, sugar syrup, gelatin, polyvinyl pyrrolidone, tragacanth and methylcellulose.

Coloring agents	Water soluble and lakolene dyes, FD & C colors, orange color paste, red color cubes, etc.
Flavorings agent	Menthol, eucalyptus oil, spearmint, cherry flavor, etc.
Whipping agent	Milk protein, egg albumin, gelatin, xanthan gum, starch, pectin, algin and carrageenan.
Humectants	Glycerin, propylene glycol and sorbitol.

7. Criteria for preparation of medicated lozenges

- a. Selection of Drug Candidate
- b. Selection of Drug Carrier

8. Method of preparation of medicated Lozenges

The technique used for the Method of preparation of medicated Lozenges is heating and congealing [Kini *et al.*,2011].

Figure 1: Method of preparation of medicated lozenges [Pattanayak and Das, 2012]

9. General consideration for designing medicated Lozenges

Since the development cost of a new chemical entity is very high, pharmaceutical companies are now focusing on the development of new drug delivery systems for existing drugs with improved efficacy and bioavailability together with reduced dosing frequency to minimize side effects. Typically, oral candidacies take the form of an adherent white, curd-like, circumscribed plaque anywhere within the oral cavity [Rawlins,1991]. There are many drugs dosage forms like lozenges, tablets, inhalers, and syrups, are in markets for the treatment of the same. The “lozenges are flavoured medicated dosage forms intended to be sucked and hold in the mouth/ pharynx. These preparations are commonly used for the purpose of local effect or systemic effect”. New drug designs to this area always beneficial for the patient, physician and drug industry. There are several dosage forms like in the market; there is a need for more dosage forms which acts effectively and locally as well as systematically [Dekker, 1991].

Table 3: The chronology of medicated lozenges (Modification in Formulation)

Year	Modification done	Advantage	Ingredients	Reference
1969	Addition of Polyethylene glycol (PEG-4000-20000), to prevent liquefaction of candy.	Large amount of medicament can be incorporated.	Sucrose, PEG (4000-20000), citric acid, glucose/ corn syrup	[Goldberg <i>et al.</i> ,1978]
1973	Replaced sugar base with gum (arabinogalactan), and to control Gumminess and stickiness of arabinogalactan with the addition of mannitol /lactose or both.	Candy were prepared with same brittleness as sucrose candy	Arabinogalactan, Mannitol/lactose, Sorbitol, citric acid: 1%, Sodium saccharin: 0.1% vegetable fat:8%, dried milk: 5%	[Addy <i>et al.</i> ,1981]
1983	Core was filled with glucose, corn syrup, Mannitol/sorbitol, or combination of these ingredients	mannitol and sorbitol acts as “sugar doctor”, inhibits crystallization of candy base	Sucrose, Mannitol/sorbitol, corn syrup, glycerine, water	[Munksgaard <i>et al.</i> , 1995]

		during storage*		
1991	Taste masked with phenol, bees wax etc.	Bitter tasted tablet became palatable.	Sodium saccharin, phenol, Mannitol (or combination)	[Weil <i>et al.</i> , 1978]
2011	Different polymers like eudragit (masked taste), NaCMC (sodium carboxymethyl cellulose) (controlled release rate), MC(increased release rate), were used for, modifying the release.	Release was increased or decreased with different polymer.	NaCMC, MC (methyl cellulose), Eudragit, Citric acid, Sucrose +dextrose	[Cafosa <i>et al.</i> , 2000]

Table 4. Medicated Lozenges Available All Over the World [Pundir and Verma ,2014]

Sr.No.	Product	Main Ingredients	Other Ingredients	Indication	Marketed by
1	VICKS®	Menthol	ascorbic acid, citric acid, eucalyptus oil, FD&C Blue No. 1, FD&C Red No. 40, flavor, liquid glucose, sucrose.	sore throat	Procter and Gamble manufacturing company
2	THERA ZINC®	Zinc (Gluconate)	Vitamin A (Acetate) 500 IU, A proprietary blend of Slippery Elm Bark (Ulmus Fulva) f Echinacea (4:1), Propolis, Elderberry, Larch and Mullein. Natural flavors.	common cold and flu	Quantum health care
3	NICORETTE®	Nicotine	aspartame, calcium polycarbophil, flavor, magnesium stearate, mannitol, potassium bicarbonate, sodium alginate, sodium carbonate, xanthan gum	smoking cessation	Perrigo company
4	STREPSILS®	Amylmetacresol, dichlorobenzyl alcohol	Hexylresorcinol, sucrose, glucose, levomenthol, blackcurrant flavour (contains propylene glycol), carmoisine	Sore throat and blocked nose	Reckitt Benkiser healthcare Ltd.

			edicol (E122), patent blue V (E131).		
5	CLOTRIMAZOLE LE LOZENGE®	Clotrimazole	Croscarmellose Sodium Dextrates, magnesium stearate, Cellulose Microcrystalline, Povidone	Oral thrush	Perrigo company
6	SUCRETS®	Dextromethorphan Hydrobromide	Corn Syrup, D&C Yellow 10, Hydrogenated Palm Oil, Menthol, N&A Honey Lemon Flavor, Sugar	Sore throat	Insight Pharmaceuticals
7	CEPACOL®	Menthol, benzocaine	cetylpyridinium chloride (Ceepryn®), glucose, peppermint oil, propylene glycol, sucrose, yellow 10	Sore throat	Combe incorporated
8	VIGROIDS®	Liquorices	Maize starch, menthol, kaolin, tragacanth, eucalyptus oil, peppermint oil, tolu tincture	Expectorant	Ernest Jackson and Company Ltd.
9	LOCKETS®	Eucalyptus and menthol	Sugar, Glucose syrup, Honey, Glycerol, Citric Acid, Vitamin C, Monopropylene Glycol, Colors E122 and E142.	Nasal congestion and sore throat	Wrigley Company

10. Evaluation parameter of Medicated Lozenges

The prepared formulations evaluated for drug content uniformity, tablet hardness, thickness and diameter, weight variation, friability and *in vitro* disintegration by pharmaceutical standard methods [Peters,2005].

- i. **Diameter** - The thickness and diameter of lozenges determined using vernier callipers. Three lozenges from each batch used and average values were calculated.
- ii. **Weight variation** - The weight variation conducted by weighing 20 lozenges individually and calculating the average weight and comparing the individual lozenges weight to the average value. Three lozenges from each batch selected and weighed individually and crushed in a mortar. Drug extracted with 100 ml of distilled water [Shojaei,1998].
- iii. **The drug content** determined spectrophotometrically at 276 nm with blank lozenge extract as the reference [Pattanayak and Das,2012].
- iv. **Hardness** - The hardness of the lozenges determined by using Monsanto Hardness tester, where the force required to break the lozenges noted [Khaladkar *et al.*,2019].
- v. **Friability** - The friability of the lozenges determined using Roche Friabilator. Weighed lozenges were placed in the friabilator and operated for 4 min at 25 rpm. The tablets then made free from dust and reweighed. The percentage friability calculated [Gopale *et al.*,2022].
- vi. **Moisture content analysis** - Moisture content in the final candy is determined by using Helium moisture balance apparatus. The sample weighed and crushed in a mortar from this one gram of the sample weighed and the moisture content is determined by the moisture balance apparatus [Rawalins,1991, Sharma *et al.*,2021].
- vii. **Mouth dissolving time test** - The time taken by the candy to dissolve completely determined by the USP Disintegration apparatus, where hard boiled candy lozenges placed in each tube of the apparatus and time taken for the lozenges to dissolve completely noted by using McIlvaine buffer, also known as a citrate-phosphate buffer of pH 6.4 at 37 °C [Choursiya and Andheriya,2018].
- viii. ***In-vitro* drug dissolution studies** - The rate of dissolution possibly is related to the efficacy of the tablet lozenge. Dissolution study carried out in 800 ml of McIlvaine buffer pH 6.4 by USP II paddle method at 150 rpm. Samples withdrawn at 5 min interval and replaced immediately with an equal volume of fresh buffer and analyzed spectrophotometrically at 276 nm.

11. Quality Control parameter [Dineshmohan *et al.*,2010]

A. Candy base – It has to be checked for following parameters-Corn syrup, sugar delivery gears, Temperature, steam pressure and cooking speed of precookers and temperature, steam pressure, cooking speed and vacuum of candy base cookers.

B. Moisture analysis –

i. **Gravimetric method-** 1g of sample is placed in vacuum oven at 60-70 °C for 12-16 hrs. After specified period of time, weigh the sample and moisture content is calculated by subtraction of final weight from initial weight.

$$\text{Moisture Content} = \text{Initial weight} - \text{final weight}$$

ii. **Karl Fisher titration-** A sample calculated to contain 10-250mg water is taken in titration flask and titrated with Karl Fischer reagent.

iii. **Azeotropic distillation method**

c) Determination of sugar and corn syrup ratios- This is done by "Dextrose equivalent method: Lane Eynon Titration method".

d) Salvage solutions- Determined using a refractometer.

e) Forming checks- Involves a check on candy rope diameter.

f) Cooling checks- Visual inspection is performed in order to analyze any stress cracking due to rapid cooling, air bubble formation, surface cracking and black specks.

g) Percentage reducing sugars-

$$\% \text{ Reducing sugar} = \frac{\text{reducing sugar factor} \times 100}{\text{Sample wt.} / 250 \times \text{Vol. of sample solution consumed by Fehlings solution}}$$

12. Microbial check

In this, the presence of any bacterial, mold or spore contamination is checked in raw materials, finished products, machinery, cooling tunnels, environmental conditions and storage drums. Laboratory microbial testing should include the following counts [Vidyadhara *et al.*,2021]:

- Total plate
- Total coliform
- Yeast and mold
- *E. coli*
- *Staphylococcus*
- *Salmonella*

13. Stability testing: The stability studies performed to assess physical as well as the chemical stability of the drug, which may possibly affect the organoleptic properties of the lozenges. Accelerated stability study conducted as per ICH guidelines (zone IV) at 45°C and 75% relative humidity over a period of seven weeks. Sufficient number of optimized formulations were packed in amber coloured screw capped bottles and kept in incubator maintained at 37°C. Samples were taken at intervals of 15 days to estimate the drug content and to evaluate organoleptic properties [Peters,2005].

A. Lozenges are subjected to stability testing under the following conditions-

- i. 1-2 months at 60 °C
- ii. 3-6 months at 45 °C

- iii. 9-12 months at 37 °C
- iv. 36-60 months at 25 °C and 40 °C.

B. Stability testing of product in package- Lozenges in their final packs are subjected to the following conditions for stability testing:

- i. 25 °C at 80% RH for 6-12 months
- ii. 37 °C at 80% RH for 3 months
- iii. 25 °C at 70% RH for 6-12 months.

14. Storage

These preparations should be stored away from heat and out of the reach of children. They should be protected from extremes of humidity. Depending on the storage requirement of both the drug and base, either room temperature or refrigerated temperature is usually indicated [**Pattanayak and Das,2012**].

15. Packaging

Hard candies are hygroscopic and usually prone to absorption of atmospheric moisture. Considerations must include the hygroscopic nature of the candy base, storage conditions of the lozenges, length of time they are stored and the potential for drug interactions. These products should be stored in tight containers to prevent drying. This is especially true for chewable lozenges that may dry out excessively and become difficult to chew. If a disposable mould with a cardboard sleeve is used, it is best to slip this unit into a properly labelled, sealable plastic bag [**Mendes and Bhargava, 2006**].

16. Applications of Lozenges:

- a. Local and systematic illness are commonly treated with lozenges.
- b. Oral thrush, sore throat, cough, gingivitis, pharyngitis, decongestants, and other oral and throat diseases can be treated and relieved by adding a range of medications to them [**Kini *et al.*,2011**].
- c. Lozenges have also been used to distribute medication in a systematic manner for smoking cessation and pain relief [**Kini *et al.*,2011**].

Conclusion

Lozenges are commonly used for localized effects in the mouth. Drugs can have a systemic effect if they are well absorbed by the buccal lining or ingested. A variety of activities can be integrated into their structure. Most preparations are available as over-the-counter medicines and can be easily administered to both pediatric and geriatric patients. It will be produced locally. Drug action includes anaesthetic, antiseptic, and antibacterial properties. lozenges were invented in the 20th century and continue to be produced commercially it's evident that lozenges offer a convenient and effective way to alleviate throat irritation, coughing, and other symptoms associated with common colds, allergies, or throat infections. Their portability, ease of use, and variety of flavours make them a popular choice for many individuals seeking relief from these discomforts. Lozenges are an important part of pharmacy and will continue to be so in the future.

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